

Deliverable D9.1: Project Management Plan - 1

Deliverable information

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Project description

Today 2.5 million tonnes of composite material are in use in the wind energy sector globally. Wind turbine blades are made up of composite materials that allow lighter and longer blades with optimised aerodynamic shape, which boost the performance of wind energy. However, current wind blade composites exhibit relatively short life spans, are problematic to repair and are notoriously difficult to recycle. As we continue to build more wind farms these issues pose a major problem to achieving a truly sustainable European wind energy sector.

EOLIAN project will develop an innovative new smart wind turbine blade, manufactured from a recyclable circular platform chemistry (vitrimers) and basal fibres, with sensors and heating actuators that detect damage early before it becomes a major issue. In the project, we will validate these performance claims through the manufacture, testing and benchmarking of a smart sensor-assisted vitrimer-based composite 14m prototyped wind blade. Additionally, we will prove circular recyclability through the manufacture of 2nd generation composites with recycled fibers and recycled vitrimer obtained after the chemical recycling by vacuum infusion and with composite parts produced by SMC following mechanical recycling.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
INEA	Innovation & Networks Executive Agency, an agency of the European Commission
HE	Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)
CFS	Certificate of the Financial Statement
VAT	Value Added Tax (a sales tax)
TBC	To be confirmed
GA	Grant Agreement

Project coordinator		
1	PROP	Proplast - Consorzio per la promozione della cultura plastica
Project beneficiaries		
2	POLM	Politecnico di milano
3	ZOREN	Zrl enerji elektrik uretim as
4	IRES	Ires - innovation in research and engineering solutions
5	NORV	Norvento tecnologia, s.l.
5,1	NNF	Norvento ned factory, s.l.u. (<i>affiliate partner to Norv</i>)
6	TEK	Fundacion Tekniker
7	EuCIA	Association Europeenne de l'industrie des Composites
8	AEP	Aep polymers srl
Project associated partners		
9	BUL	Brunel University London
10	ENT	Entelea limited

1 Introduction

This Project Management Plan represents the first version and presents information for the consortium members of the EOLIAN project to understand the processes, procedures, roles and obligations of each partner. The processes and procedures described are to ensure an effective and clearly define methodology for ensuring that the Project is delivered as efficiently as possible. This document complements existing project documentation including the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement and should be used in conjunction with these two documents.

The aim of this document is to provide guidelines and procedures which should be followed within the EOLIAN project to ensure that the project is delivered according to the Description of Action in the Grant Agreement.

This project management plan is intended to be a live document and although no significant changes to this document are envisaged, the guidance and some sections may be updated based on the decisions of the Project Executive Board, through personnel changes or changes to the project Description of Action which will require an update to this document.

This plan is based on several key documents/meetings including:

- The EOLIAN Consortium Agreement – based on the DESCA - DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1.1, November 2022 (www.DESCA-2020.eu)
- The EOLIAN Grant Agreement – GA Number 101147532

2 Organization, governance and decision making

The organisational structure of the consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

- The **General Assembly**, as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium.
- The **Project Management Board** as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.
- The **Coordinator** as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.
- **External Expert Advisory board.**

2.1.1 General Assembly

The General Assembly shall consist of one representative of each Party (hereinafter General Assembly Member). The General Assembly shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein. In addition, all proposals made by the Project Management Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the General Assembly.

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

- Content, finances and intellectual property rights,
- Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority,
- Changes to the Consortium Plan,
- Modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 (Background Included)
- Additions to Attachment 3 (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.3.2)
- Additions to Attachment 4 (Identified entities under the same control)

Evolution of the consortium

- Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement

Breach, defaulting party status and litigation

- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto
- Steps to be taken for litigation purposes and the coverage of litigation costs in case of joint claims of the parties of the consortium against a Party

Appointments

On the basis of the Grant Agreement, the appointment, if necessary, of:

- Project Management Board Members
- External Expert Advisory Board Members

	Organisation	Assigned representatives
1	PROP	Marco Monti, (Marta Zaccone)
2	POLM	Marco Luigi Longana, (Claudia Marano)
3	ZOREN	Zeynep Korkmaz, (Nilgun Kurtcu)
4	IRES	Foteini Petrakli, (Elias Koumoulos)
5	NORV	Rafael Pardo Crespo, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
5.1	NNF	Rafael Pardo Crespo, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
6	TEK	Miren Blanco, (Cristina Monteserin)
7	EuCIA	Raphael Pleyner, (Amanda Jacob)
8	AEP	Andrea Minigher, (Walter Pitacco)
9	BUL	Daniel Paul, (Nithin Amirth Jayasree)
10	ENT	Dimitrios Anastasiou, (Kostas Papadopoulos)

2.1.2 Project Management Board

The Project Management Board shall consist of the Coordinator and the representatives of the Parties appointed to it by the General Assembly.

The Project Management Board shall:

- prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly,
- seek a consensus among the Parties

- be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly
- monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project
- collect information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly
- support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables
- support the dissemination activity leader to prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section "Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility" and of Section 8 of this Consortium Agreement

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the Project Management Board shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

	Organisation	Assigned representatives
1	PROP	Marco Monti, (Marta Zaccone)
2	POLM	Marco Luigi Longana, (Claudia Marano)
3	ZOREN	Zeynep Korkmaz, (Nilgun Kurtcu)
4	IRES	Foteini Petrakli, (Elias Koumoulos)
5	NORV	Rafael Pardo Crespo, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
5,1	NNF	Rafael Pardo Crespo, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
6	TEK	Miren Blanco, (Cristina Monteserin)
7	EuCIA	Raphael Pleynet, (Amanda Jacob)
8	AEP	Andrea Minigher, (Walter Pitacco)
9	BUL	Daniel Paul, (Nithin Amirth Jayasree)
10	ENT	Dimitrios Anastasiou, (Kostas Papadopoulos)

2.1.3 Coordinator

The Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in this Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks

- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.
- Calling all the meeting, proposing the decisions and preparing the agenda of the General Assembly meetings, presiding over the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of the decisions taken during the meetings.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any Project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other 'Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

2.1.4 Work Package Leaders

In the following table the representatives of each partner, that is work package leader is reported.

WP	Assigned leader	Assigned leader
1	ZORLU	Zeynep Korkmaz
2	Tekniker	Miren Blanco
3	POLIMI	Marco Luigi Longana
4	Tekniker	Alazne Martinez
5	AEP	Andrea Minigher
6	Proplast	Ilaria Poncini
7	IRES	Foteini Petrakli
8	EuCIA	Amanda Jacob
9	Proplast	Marco Monti

2.2 Organization meetings and procedures

2.2.1 Frequency of consortium meetings

The constituted meeting frequencies for the General Assembly and Executive board are detailed below:

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	At least once a year	At any time upon request of the Project Management Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Project Management Board	At least quarterly	At any time upon request of any Member of the Project Management Board

2.2.2 Notice of meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Project Management Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

2.2.3 Sending the agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	7 calendar days

2.2.4 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	2 calendar days

During a meeting the Members of a Consortium Body present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

2.2.5 Decisions

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if

- a) the Coordinator circulates to all Members of the General Assembly a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after receipt by a Party and
- b) the decision is agreed by 51 % of all Parties.

The Coordinator shall inform all the Parties of the outcome of the vote.

A veto may be submitted up to 15 calendar days after receipt of this information.

The decision will be binding after the Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

3 Communication strategy

3.1 Internal

3.1.1 EOLIAN OneDrive share folder

A Microsoft Teams repository has been created by the Coordinator, where all the documents are available at any time to the Consortium members.

3.1.2 Partners contact list

A partner contact list has been created by the Coordinator as an excel file and shared by the repository. It will be updated upon request of the partners.

3.1.3 Teleconferencing

Microsoft Teams will be preferably used for telcos throughout the duration of the project.

3.1.4 Meetings

Prior to a meeting or telephone conference a calling notice should be issued. The calling notice sets the time and date of the meeting, identifies the attendees who should participate in the meeting, the aims and objectives of the meeting, the agenda and reference to any supporting documentation which should be read prior to the meeting taking place.

If there is a physical meeting the calling notice should also contain the meeting location, and recommended travel arrangement and accommodation.

Calling notices for teleconferences may be issued by task leaders and work package leaders as appropriate.

For work package meetings, the agenda should be issued two weeks before the meeting and any changes to the agenda should be sent at least 7 days before the meeting (Note: these periods differ from those for the formal Project Management Board or General Assembly).

The minutes of the meeting should be taken and a draft of the minutes should be made available 14 days after the end of the meeting. The minutes should be circulated to all parties concerned for comments or approval, upon issuing the minutes a deadline should be set for the return of comments and in the absence of comments beyond the deadline the minutes are deemed to be approved.

Minutes from work package and task meetings should be stored in the folder for the appropriate work package.

The minutes will reflect any issues discussed within the meeting, conclusions and actions agreed. A template of the minutes showing the structure, and the content is stored on the Microsoft Teams.

3.1.5 Absences

If any member of the Executive Board, work package leader or task leader expects to be absent from work or unable to fulfil their duties for a significant period of time this should be reported to the project management team and a nominated contact/replacement should be assigned to cover their duties.

The project management team will produce a list of deliverable due dates, the review periods for each deliverable and a list of participants involved in the deliverable review process. If any participant is expecting to be absent during one of these review periods which would result in them being unable to fulfil their duties, they should notify the project management team in order to allow them to assign a replacement.

3.2 External communication and dissemination

3.2.1 Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy has the purpose to ensure that the results from the EOLIAN project are disseminated to end-users and researchers, ensuring the implementation of the products from this project and that any future or on-going research builds upon and does not duplicate the work of the EOLIAN project.

The dissemination of the project outcomes and any publications have been planned in the specific Deliverable 8.1 Plan for dissemination & exploitation, incl. communication activities.

4 Procedure for technical monitoring

An excel file has been created as a valuable tool for the project management plan. It highlights the most important information and is divided in different spreadsheets, as follows.

Project overview. It reports the most important information about the project, e.g. title and acronym, GA number, starting date, duration, partner list.

WP. It reports the list of WPs and Tasks, with WP leaders and participants.

GANTT. It reports the GANTT chart of the project with two more columns where to report the eventual shift.

Deliverable. It reports the list of the deliverables, with the related WP, the responsible of the preparation, the dissemination level, the type of deliverable, the planned delivery date. There is also a last column with the potential shift needed, to be used only in the case the partner responsible highlight it in due time.

Milestone. It reports the list of the milestones, with the related WP, the responsible of the attainment, the planned date. There is also a last column with the potential shift needed, to be used only in the case the partner responsible highlight it in due time.

Project timeline and deadlines. It helps the monitoring of the deadlines.

The last spreadsheets are related to project activities and will be used to record information regarding specific technical activities and for the risk management. These spreadsheets will be updated during the project implementation. They are:

Action tracker. It reports information regarding specific key actions.

The excel file is under the control of the management team of the coordinator, and it can be available to the project officer upon request, at any time.

5 Procedure for deliverables preparation

5.1 Structure of deliverables

Each deliverable should follow a set structure as set out in the templates of:

- Deliverable information
- Revision and history chart
- Project description
- Table of Contents
- Abbreviations and Acronyms
- Introduction of the objectives of the deliverable
- Main body of the report – this section will explain the task that was carried out and the results generated and illustrate the technical and scientific progress made within the task.
- Conclusions – these sections should be a summary of the major outputs of the deliverable and the implications of the results on other parts of the project or the impact on that the results will have for the end-users and the railway community. The conclusions should also highlight the deficiencies in the work carried out and where future improvements or further work should be directed.
- References, if any
- Annexes – Annexes of data or further information not suitable for the main body of the report either due to its detailed nature or separated for confidentiality purposes (if any).

5.2 Tracking of deliverables and review process

A specific procedure has been set up for the deliverable preparation timeline, to guarantee the compliance with the planned deadline. As reported in the previous chapter, a dedicated spreadsheet, which describes all the deliverables, their submission dates with the corresponding project month and each deliverable responsible, has been prepared.

It was designed as a helpful instrument for the Coordinator to apply the procedure, reported as follows:

- a remind message, related to the submission date of each deliverable, has been fixed internally among the Coordinator team members, 60 days before its deadline;
- the same remind message will be sent to the responsible partner of each deliverable by the Coordinator 60 days before its deadline;
- each deliverable has to be delivered to the Coordinator by the responsible partner in a draft form at least 15 days before the submission date in order to be able to be reviewed from both technical and formal points of view;
- after potential revisions of the deliverable, it will be submitted to the EU portal;
- if a critical issue in preparing the deliverable on time are detected, its responsible partner shall inform the Coordinator immediately. In this way, the Coordinator will be able to handle the situation and inform the PO.

5.3 Dissemination level of deliverables

During the proposal stage it was agreed that most of the EOLIAN deliverables would have a public dissemination level meaning that they will be made available to anyone, and this is to ensure that the results of the project can reach the largest audience possible. However, particular tasks may need to use data or information which is confidential or commercially valuable, in which case a subset or example of such data or information will be presented in the public deliverable. Detailed confidential information may be presented within internal reports or could be presented within separate confidential annexes to the main public deliverable.

5.4 Milestones

The EOLIAN milestones are not subject to the same review process as the deliverables and are mainly as a project management tool to ensure that progress is being made. Each milestone will be assessed against a quality criteria by the Project Management Team and progress, or completion status will be logged by the Project Management Team and reported to the Project Executive Board as an indicator of progress.

Project milestones are listed in the Grant Agreement Pag. 35, list of milestones.

6 Documents management

It is expected that over the course of the EOLIAN project that many documents will be produced, it is therefore vital that document management processes are followed in order to enable users to locate and identify relevant files and to ensure version control.

6.1 Storage

All documents produced in the project will be stored and archived on the extranet site (Microsoft Teams repository), with a folder for each work package including the WP9 Project Management and additional folders for General Documents, Meetings and Administrative documents. The Deliverables will be uploaded in a specific folder of the General section: Working reports will be uploaded in the WP folders, and documents related to meetings will be uploaded in the Meeting folders.

6.2 Document templates

Document templates have been produced which use a standard format including defined styles, page layout and content structure. These templates have been prepared by the Project Management Team are available on the extranet site under General Documents/Templates.

Templates have been produced for:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Meeting Calling Notices (MS Word format)
- Meeting Minutes (MS Word format)
- Presentations (MS Powerpoint format)

7 Procedure for technical review report preparation

According to GA, technical reports will be prepared at M14, 28, 42. They will contain an update of the outcomes achieved in the reporting period they are related to.

A specific procedure has been set up for the technical review report preparation timeline, to guarantee the compliance with the planned deadline, as follows:

- a remind message, related to the submission date of the report, has been fixed internally among the Coordinator team members, 90 days before its deadline;
- the same remind message will be sent to the responsible partner of each WP by the Coordinator 90 days before its deadline;

- each WP technical report has to be delivered to the Coordinator by the responsible partner in a draft form at least 20 days before the submission date in order to be able to be reviewed from both technical and formal points of view;
- after potential revisions of the report, it will be submitted to the EU portal.

8 Financial management

8.1 Procedure for financial monitoring

A specific procedure has been set up for the financial monitoring to guarantee the compliance with the deadline establish in the Grant Agreement.

It is essential to monitoring the actual progress with a reporting system. In order to check the progress of the project expenditure and the related personnel/months, the Coordinator has decided to require to all beneficiaries an internal financial report in addition to the mandatory financial reports at months 14, 28 and 42.

8.2 Procedure for the internal financial reporting period

The internal financial report is the second part of the mandatory internal progress report. The internal financial report documents the planned person months, and the actual person months used per work package and task in the previous 7 months. This must be completed and uploaded in the dedicated share folder by each partner every 7 months.

The procedure will be:

- the Coordinator will send a reminding message and uploaded the common file excel to be completed in the share folder 15 days before the end of the period;
- the partners will have to complete the excel file within 20 days of the end of the period.

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8.3 Mandatory financial reporting period

The financial report consists of structured forms in the participant's portal grant management system including:

- Individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the Grant Agreement) for each consortium member explanation of the use of resources from each consortium member for the reporting period concerned.
- a periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

The participant portal tool for reporting is SyGMa which opens for periodic reporting (PP) at the end of the reporting period on M14, 28 and 42. There is a 60-day period in which to complete the report. However, the Coordinator will ask to the partners to complete the financial report by 30-day after the end of the period in order to check and approve the expenditures.

8.4 Keeping Records

Records and supporting documentation generated during the project must be kept for five years after the payment of the balance as required in the article 20 of the Grant Agreement. See the GA for detailed information.

8.5 Payment handling

All Horizon Europe projects have a co-ordinator, the EC will pay all the money on behalf of the project to this co-ordinator in this case this is Proplast. The co-ordinator is then responsible for distributing the money to the other partners of the project.

The maximum total EC financial contribution for EOLIAN is fixed at 3'653'176.25€.

8.5.1 Pre-financing.

This is made at the start of the project, usually within 30 days of the EC signing the Grant Agreement.

The pre-finance payment made to the co-ordinator will be 52.50% of the Maximum EC Financial Contribution less the 5% contribution the guarantee fund. This translates into pre-financing of 1'918'240.77€. Of this 1'735'581.96€ is transferred to the consortium (coordinator) and 182'658.81€ kept by the Commission for the Guarantee Fund.

- Interim Payments.

These are made after each period financial reports are submitted and accepted by EC. The interim payment, similar to the initial prepayment, will be limited to 90% of the Maximum EC Financial Contribution.

- Final Payment.

This is made at the end of the project once EC has accepted all deliverables and reports and will include any final payment due to the project. This will include the Guarantee Fund payment.

- Guarantee Fund

The Guarantee Fund is a percentage of the budget, in the case of EOLIAN the EC withholds 5% of each partner's budget at the start of the project in the Guarantee Fund. If the project runs smoothly and there are no issues this 5% is paid out by the EC with the final payment.

The EC use the money in this fund to reimburse the project in the situation where one of the partners is made bankrupt and takes with it money in excess of the costs reported.

8.5.2 Distribution of funds to partners

The EC financial contribution is received by the Project Coordinator on behalf of the consortium, split by the number of reporting periods. The Project Co-ordinator will then distribute the EC financial contribution to each partner without unjustified delay according to the rules set out in the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement.

9 Risk Management Documentation

The "Issue Register" is a log of any issue which arises during the course of the project and will be maintained by the Project Manager. The Issue Register will collate any issue as it arises, issues will then be analysed and escalated or dealt with accordingly. An issue could be anything which is of concern to a partner, Work Package Leader or the Executive Committee, this could be deviations from the project plan, identification of new risks or just concerns. For example it may be an issue

such as Partner X is not responding to emails, this may be a precursor to larger problems which may impact on the work programme, therefore, as an issue is raised it may cause a trigger which causes a new risk to be identified and added to the risk register and contingency plans to be devised or it may result in the Project Executive Board proposing actions are taken.

It is the role of the Project Manager to sort and assign the actions to items raised on the Issue Register and ensure that the actions are followed up. However, it is the role of all consortium members, third parties and User Group members to raise issues and present them to the Project Manager.

9.1 Risk management and risk register

A list of risks was identified during the grant preparation stage and reviewed at the kick-off meeting. This risk register will be maintained and updated throughout the project, each WP leader is expected to identify any new risks occurring within or affecting their work package and the Project Executive Board identify any global risks which may have an impact across the work packages.

Each risk will be assessed by the Project Management Board for its criticality to the overall plan of work and normal risk assessment techniques such as a likelihood/severity matrix can be used for assessing the potential risk impact and therefore the requirement for the implementation of a contingency plan.

The risk register will be reviewed by the Project Management Board at each board meeting, any new risks identified updated, assessed and contingency plans created if necessary. The Executive Board will also assess whether the likelihood or severity of existing risks have changed and create or updated the contingency plans. If a contingency plan results in a change to GA Annex 1 a proposal for the change should be proposed by the Project Management Board for approval by the General Assembly.

In order to manage and register the risks of the project, the file created for the project management has only a spreadsheet to report the potential issues, how it may affect the attainment of the objectives, and how it can be faced.

The table with the Risk Guidance is the follow:

				Minimal	Minor	Moderate	Major	Severe
	Low %	High %		1	2	3	4	5
Not Likely	0	10	1	1	3	5	9	12
Low Likelihood	11	30	2	2	4	11	15	17
Likely	31	70	3	6	10	14	19	21
Highly Likely	71	90	4	7	13	18	22	24
Near Certain	91	100	5	8	16	20	23	25

	Minimal	Minor	Moderate	Major	Severe
Performance					
Time	< 5 days	5 - 10 days	10 - 20 days	20 - 30 days	> 30 days
Cost					

% Probability: An estimated **percentage value** of the likelihood of the risk occurring, as per the following scale and criteria:

%	%		
1	10	Not Likely	Unlikely. History of similar process shows no failures
11	30	Low Likelihood	Few number of occurrences likely
31	70	Medium Likelihood	Frequent occurrences are likely
71	90	High Likelihood	High number of occurrences are likely
91	100	Almost certain	Almost certain to occur. History of many occurrences with previous or similar designs/causes

Impact: Drop-down menu of the severity terms, as per the following scale and criteria, to provide an estimate of the severity of the impact of the risk should it occur:

Minimal	1	No Effect
	2	Very slight effect on performance. Customer not annoyed. Non-vital fault noticed sometimes.
	3	Slight effect on performance. Customer slightly annoyed. Non-vital fault noticed most of the time.
Minor	4	Minor effect on performance. Fault does not require repair. Customer will notice minor effect on product or its performance. Non-vital fault always noticed.
	5	Moderate effect on performance. Customer experiences some dissatisfaction. Fault on non-vital part requires repair.
Moderate	6	Product performance degraded, but operable and safe. Customer experiences discomfort. Non-vital part inoperable.
	7	Product performance severely affected, but still safe. Customer dissatisfied. Subsystem inoperable.
Major	8	Product inoperable but safe. Customer very dissatisfied. Device inoperable.
	9	Potentially hazardous effect. Able to achieve safe state without mishap - gradual failure. Compliance with regulations in jeopardy.
Severe	10	Hazardous effect. Safety related - sudden failure. Non-compliance with Government regulation.

Proximity: Drop-down menu of the predicted timescales within which you would expect and anticipate the risk (threat or opportunity) to occur:

Imminent	within 2 weeks
Within WP	within the timescales of the present work package,
Within Project	within the timescales of the entire project
Beyond Project	beyond the timescales of the entire project

10 Conclusions

The project management plan presented in the document provides a guide to be used by the Project Management Team and the consortium partners to ensure an understanding of the roles and responsibilities of each member of the consortium in delivering the EOLIAN project through efficient and well managed processes. This document should be used by partners to complement the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Further guidelines may also be found on the EC Participant Portal within the Horizon Europe Online Manual

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>

If any item in this document is ambiguous, or further assistance or advise is required then please contact the Project Management Team:

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